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Two Rare Marine Gastropods from the Shores of Phaselis (Gulf of Antalya)

Phaselis Kıyılarından (Antalya Körfezi) İki Ender Gastropod Türü

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Abstract: Two relatively rare Mediterranean gastropods, *Cima cylindrica* and *Cima minima* (family Cimidae) have been found in samples collected near the shore at Phaselis. These are the first records of these species from the coasts of Türkiye.

Keywords: Mollusca, Snail, Fauna, Biodiversity

Öz: Phaselis kıyılarında yeni bulunan iki ender denizel gastropod türü, *Cima cylindrica* ve *Cima minima* (familya Cimidae), Türkiye kıyıları için ilk kayıtlardır.

Anahtar sözcükler: Mollusca, Salyangoz, Fauna, Biyolojik Çeşitlilik

Introduction

We started to survey the marine molluscs along the shores of Phaselis in 2020. Our preliminary results so far indicate the presence of a rich fauna. The total number of gastropod species alone has approached 100; a relatively high number considering the shoreline length of less than 1000 m and the collection depth of less than 10 m that we have so far sampled. Our results will be published in a series of papers in the near future. Presently, we report the recent finding of two relatively rare marine snails.

Materials and Methods

Samples of shell grit (mixture of fine sand, shells and shell fragments) were collected during snorkel dives. The material was dried and then sieved through sieves with openings of 0.5, 1, 2 and 4 mm. The shells in the finest fractions were removed under a stereomicroscope. Shells were measured with a calibrated eye-piece reticle under a stereomicroscope. Photographs of shells taken at different focus levels were stacked using Helicon Focus (Helicon Soft).

Collecting and processing of the samples were done by the first author, identifications by the second author. Abbreviations: CMNH, Carnegie Museum of Natural History, Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, U.S.A.

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Results and Discussion

We found two shells of *Cima cylindrica* (Jeffreys, 1856) and one shell of *Cima minima* (Jeffreys, 1858) in shell grit taken in May 2022. The sample was collected at depths of 2-3 m on rocky bottoms in the North Harbor and just outside the Central Harbor of Phaselis¹.

The larger *Cima cylindrica* shell was 1.1 mm in height (Fig. 1) and the smaller one was 0.9 mm. Faint spiral lines, a characteristic of the species², were visible at high magnifications on teleoconch whorls, especially on body whorls (Figs. 1, 2b). The protoconch had a smooth surface and the transition to the teleoconch was not distinct (Fig. 2A); a small, partially encrusted umbilicus outside the columellar edge was visible (Fig. 2b). Both specimens have been deposited in CMNH (CM 180001).

Fig. 1. *Cima cylindrica* (shell height, 1.1 mm).

Fig. 2a. Apex of the *Cima cylindrica* shell in Fig. 1. Bottom of the body whorl of the smaller *Cima cylindrica* shell. Partially encrusted umbilicus (arrow) and the spiral microsculpture are visible.

Fig. 3. *Cima minima* (shell height, 1.5 mm).

The *Cima minima* shell was 1.5 mm in height (Fig. 3). Its teleoconch whorls had closely spaced, fine, radial growth lines, but no spirals, in agreement with literature descriptions³. The specimen has been deposited in CMNH (CM 180002).

Both species are native to the Mediterranean Sea, but probably because of their small sizes, have been recorded infrequently and either mentioned only by name or not included at all in some guides to Mediterranean molluscs⁴. Neither species was listed in the most recent compilation of the marine molluscs of Türkiye⁵. The present records are the first of these species for the coasts of Türkiye.

Despite the heavy use of the beaches of Phaselis by swimmers and the frequenting of the bays by boats during spring and summer months, the area remains relatively well conserved and is mostly free from coastal development. We believe that the preservation of the shore habitats is contributing to the presence of not only a rich mollusc fauna, but also of other marine life⁶.

¹ Aslan & Baybo 2015.

² Aartsen 1981; Oliver *et al.* 2015.

³ Aartsen 1981; Jeffreys 1867, 115; Gofas *et al.* 2011, 360.

⁴ Poppe & Goto 1991, 187; Alf *et al.* 2020, 235.

⁵ Öztürk *et al.* 2014.

⁶ Yavuz & Tunç 2015; Gökoğlu *et al.* 2018.

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